

OVERALL DIGITAL SERVICES CATALOGUE

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1. Executive summary

This document is the fourth in a line of deliverables aimed at tracking the development of AgrifoodTEF’s digital services. The first of this line was D2.1 (*Digital infrastructure requirements and initial catalogue of services*, due at M6); the last three are yearly editions of the current document (D2.14, D2.15, D2.16: *Overall digital services catalogue*).

2025 has been the year when service delivery by AgrifoodTEF partners to customers took flight. At the time of writing (beginning of December 2025) the number of services negotiated with customers is over 450. Of these, a significant fraction are digital services, i.e. the focus of this Deliverable. For comparison, at the end of 2024 the number of digital services activated was (as documented by D2.15) around 20.

As the activities of AgrifoodTEF develop, the documents in this line of deliverables progressively shift their focus from tracking service *offering* to tracking service *provision*. This shift reflects the need to focus on extracting guidelines from experience and on defining sustainability pathways for AgrifoodTEF after the end of the 5-year project span. We are now approaching a stage where the development of mechanisms for service delivery and (eventually) for AgrifoodTEF self-sustainability can be switched from *open-loop* (i.e., driven by partners’ provisions and previous experience) to *closed-loop*, i.e. driven by the actual demands and expectations of our customers.

The evolution of this line of deliverables and the parallel shift in their goals is summarised by the following table, where D2.16 represents this document.

Year	Document	Main focus	Main goal
Y1 (2023)	D2.1	Design of service catalogue features and access mechanisms	Define design guidelines for the service catalogue
	D2.14	Overview of digital services <u>planned by partners</u>	Document the development of services
Y2 (2024)	D2.15	Analysis of digital services <u>listed in the catalogue</u> ; feedback from providers of first digital services	Provide indications to improve service offering and execution
Y3 (2025)	D2.16	Analysis of activities <u>contracted between service providers and customers</u> ; analysis of tools for sustainability	Understand the market for AgrifoodTEF services; provide indications to set up sustainability mechanisms

For the next release of this document, due at the end of 2026, we will strive to make a further step forward: i.e., the incorporation of customer feedback in the analysis. For this we plan to coordinate with Work Package 4, which includes activities aimed at collecting feedback from customers.

Coming back to the current edition of this Deliverable (D2.16: *Overall Digital Service Catalogue Y3*), its main goal is to analyse the market for AgrifoodTEF services and –based on such analysis– outline tools for sustainability. The input for the analysis comes from the contracts signed between AgrifoodTEF customers and the partners providing services to them. The contents of this document are structured as follows.

Section 2 explores AgrifoodTEF activities contracted between service providers and customers. This deliverable is the first one in its line where it is possible to do this, i.e., to use as the source of data service *request* by customers instead of service *offering* by AgrifoodTEF.

Section 3 explains why, due to their inherent properties, digital services have the possibility of playing a key role in the sustainability of AgrifoodTEF after the end of the project.

Section 4 is dedicated to the tools that AgrifoodTEF is building to sustain its long-term sustainability, focusing on those related to digital services. For reasons that will be described in Section 3, sustainability tools connected to digital services promote the sustainability of the whole set of AgrifoodTEF services: therefore, the relevance of Section 4 is not constrained to digital services. Section 4 will devote special attention to the activities connected to the management of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) for data: this aspect is, in fact, very important for sustainability.

Section 5 concludes the document and provides actionable guidelines to promote the sustainability of the TEF after the end of the AgrifoodTEF project.

Annex 1 to this document is a focused analysis supporting the discussion on IPR of Section 4. Annex 1 defines the constraints imposed by the EU Data Act on the IPR management of data generated by AgrifoodTEF digital services and explores the compatibility between the IPR mechanisms of AgrifoodTEF and the pre-existing *EU Code of conduct on agricultural data sharing by contractual agreement* (EUCC).

2. Understanding AgrifoodTEF's market

As anticipated by Section 1, service provision by AgrifoodTEF partners is now well underway. During 2025 the preparatory and setup activities needed to build the complex technical and administrative machinery required by AgrifoodTEF finally approached completion, and partners started to focus their efforts towards reaching customers and offering them services. The consequent increase in the number of services contracted is readily apparent: the number of services contracted went from a few tens at the end of 2024 to more than 450 at the end of 2025.

This section is dedicated to analysing the composition and nature of the **activities** executed by AgrifoodTEF to support its customers.

We define an activity as *the full set of actions that the partner servicing a customer enacts in order to satisfy the contract signed with the customer*. Generally, an activity is a comprehensive “service package” that comprises multiple items, connected into a structured whole covering all aspects of the customer’s request formalised by the contract. Analysing activities allows AgrifoodTEF to understand better what its customers (current and potential) expect from it. An activity, differently from the individual services it comprises, describes all the aspects of an integrated action and is therefore a much more complete picture of what AgrifoodTEF customers require.

A good tool to track activities are the **Service Request Forms (SRFs)**, i.e. the documents that partners submit to AgrifoodTEF’s Onboarding Committee to ask for approval prior to the signature of a service contract. Each Service Request Form outlines an activity and the service package aimed at executing it. The SRF provides a description of the customer, of its field of operation, of the solution to be tested and –most importantly– of the set of actions that the service provider will execute for (and with) the customer after the signature of the contract.

For this analysis we examined each one of the 241 Service Request Forms submitted to the Onboarding Committee from the beginning of the project up to December 4th, 2025. Most of these SRFs correspond to service packages including multiple, interconnected services. A comparison between the number of services contracted and the number of SRFs shows that the average number of services per SRF is around 2.

The activities described by the Service Request Forms have been subdivided into the following four categories:

- “mainly **physical**”: i.e., where the main focus of the activity is on physical services;
- “mainly **digital**”: i.e., where the main focus of the activity is on digital services;
- “mainly **conformity-related**”: i.e., where the main focus of the activity is on conformity services;
- “mainly **other**”: i.e., not corresponding to any of the previous categories.

The word “mainly” highlights how the activity described by a Service Request Forms often involves elements belonging to multiple categories. Activity categorisation is therefore a somewhat subjective task that relies on capturing the focus of the activity, i.e. estimating what action(s) require the greater part of the effort to be executed by the service provider.

The categories used for activities are based on the following definitions of physical, digital and conformity services:

- A service is a *physical service* if its execution makes use of AgrifoodTEF’s physical infrastructure. A physical service may or may not make use of AgrifoodTEF’s digital infrastructure. AgrifoodTEF’s *physical infrastructure*

comprises the systems which require physical interaction with the customer’s solution for the service to take place.

- A service is a *digital service* if its execution makes use of AgrifoodTEF's digital infrastructure and does not make use of AgrifoodTEF's physical infrastructure. AgrifoodTEF's *digital infrastructure* comprises the systems which do not require physical interaction with the customer’s solution for the service to take place, and which can be accessed remotely.
- A service is a *conformity service* if its goal is to assess, promote and/or document the compliance of the customer's systems with standards, norms, practices or regulations defined outside of AgrifoodTEF. Execution of a conformity service may or may not make use of AgrifoodTEF's physical or digital infrastructure.

Analysis of AgrifoodTEF activities

Figure 2.1 provides a breakdown of the activities corresponding to the 241 Service Request Form into the four categories described above, in terms of absolute numbers and of percentages.

Figure 2.1: distribution of AgrifoodTEF activities described by Service Request Forms

From a first examination of these charts it appears that the majority of AgrifoodTEF’s activities are “mainly physical”. “Mainly digital” activities come second, and numerically account for 2/3 of the “mainly physical” ones. Finally, “mainly conformity-related” activities account for ~1/3 of the “mainly digital” ones, or 1/4 of the “mainly physical” ones. Overall, “mainly physical” and “mainly digital” activities together cover 80% of the total.

“Mainly physical” activities

The prevalence of “mainly physical” appears coherent with the fact that most of the activities concern agriculture, which is an inherently physical activity. However, this first view does not provide the complete picture. In fact, as explained, the categorisation of activities provided by the charts concerns the main *focus* of the activities in terms of effort, but it does not capture their internal articulation. Going deeper in the analysis of Service Request Forms, it becomes apparent that “mainly physical” activities have a significantly more diverse composition than the other categories. More specifically: while most of the “mainly conformity” and “mainly digital” activities comprise only actions strictly related to their categorisation, a significant fraction of the actions in “mainly physical” activities are not physical at all. More specifically: they are data-related.

The Service Request Forms show that it is common for activities classified as “mainly physical” to expend a significant part of their effort in setting up specific physical environments and infrastructure and then proceeding to use them to collect agriculture-related data. The data are then provided to the customer as a key part of the activity, sometimes after validation and/or processing (e.g., labelling) by the service provider. Figure 2.2 provides quantitative evidence of this trend.

“Mainly physical” SRFs including dataset generation and provision activities

Figure 2.2: percentage of “mainly physical” activities involving dataset generation and provision

In practice, many of the “mainly physical” activities of AgrifoodTEF are focused on performing physical activities concerning the use of a physical system (e.g., a ground robot or a drone, either autonomous or teleoperated) to collect real-world data about a physical environment of agricultural significance, such as a given culture at a specified growth stage in specified climatic conditions. Sometimes the environment is prepared specifically for the data collection as part of the activity, sometimes it is picked from available options. All the actions connected to preparation of the environment and the infrastructure used for data acquisition are “physical” inasmuch they require significant physical

operations; however, the ultimate *goal* of such actions is in itself “digital”: i.e., (making the service provider able to) provide the customer with the datasets they requested.

Among the 45% of “mainly physical” activities that include data acquisition and provision, many activities comprise *only the actions strictly needed for that*, and nothing else. The strong weight of data generation among “mainly physical” activities is relevant to AgrifoodTEF’s sustainability, for the reasons explained below.

If a service provider collects (possibly as a consequence of AgrifoodTEF activities) a sufficiently large *corpus* of data covering a sufficiently wide range of conditions of agricultural significance, that partner can leverage such *corpus* to provide data provision services to other customers in the future, without need to proceed again to the physical activity of data collection. The possibility of doing so increases if multiple service providers (such as AgrifoodTEF partners) all contribute datasets to a common *corpus*, and are able to exploit the whole joint *corpus* to provide services to customers.

It appears, then, that many of today’s “mainly physical” activities may be seen as preliminary and preparatory to future “mainly digital” ones. Given the large advantage in execution costs that digital activities have over physical ones, such a shift over time of AgrifoodTEF’s from physical to digital can contribute to AgrifoodTEF’s long-term sustainability. Section 3 explores this issue in more detail.

The possibility for an AgrifoodTEF service provider to exploit the data collected while executing an activity for a customer today to provide other services to other customers in the future is not to be taken for granted. On the contrary, it requires to be recognised and exploited. This in turn means that it must be negotiated with the original customer and suitably formalised in the service contract. This issue is critically linked to the management of Intellectual Property Rights concerning the data generated by AgrifoodTEF services: a topic which is further explored by Section 4.

“Mainly digital” activities

We have so far focused this analysis on “mainly physical” activities because they provide relevant insights concerning the self-sustainability of TEF activities after the end of the AgrifoodTEF project. Let us now shift our attention towards “mainly digital” ones.

As already noted, “mainly digital” activities are considerably less composite in their internal structure when compared to “mainly physical” ones: i.e., “mainly digital” activities often do not include any physical- or conformity-related action. In many cases, these activities reflect the current interest towards the application of AI models to a wide range of applications previously tackled via classical algorithmic approaches. More specifically, many “mainly digital” Service Request Forms concern one or more of the actions required to train an AI model, such as:

- provision of the computing infrastructure needed for training or testing activities;
- provision of datasets suitable for training or testing;
- data processing (e.g., validation, cleaning, labeling);
- execution of tests on AI models (e.g., validation in different conditions and/or with suitably prepared data);

- identification of shortcomings, weaknesses and elements suitable to improvement.

It is possible to gain additional insight into why customers contract “mainly digital” activities with AgrifoodTEF by going down to the level of individual services via the PowerBi data analysis package, applied to service data. The graph in Figure 2.3 is a breakdown of service value by use case. As anticipated, it shows how AI is indeed the main driver of AgrifoodTEF services in terms of value. Almost 2/3 (66%) of the total revenue of AgrifoodTEF from service execution is, in fact, associated to the “AI” macro use case.

Figure 2.3: breakdown of service value for the “AI” macro use case

The graph above also illustrates how the “AI” macro use case maps onto sectorial use cases, i.e. to what fields of activity AgrifoodTEF customers plan to apply the results of our services. Here it appears clearly how most of our customers are interested in applying to arable farming the solutions they brought to AgrifoodTEF. For what concerns the subdivision of the “arable farming” sectorial use case into activity use cases, a large majority of our customers’ interest goes towards observation and monitoring (e.g., checking culture state or detecting disease). The tools chosen by our customers to perform such operations are for the most part AI models, which confirms the outcomes of the activity-level analysis performed on Service Request Forms.

While this document is mainly interested in digital services, we provide for completeness, in Figure 2.4, the corresponding service value breakdown graph for the “Robotics” macro use case. This confirms how arable farming is the most interesting application according to AgrifoodTEF’s customers. In this case, the activity use case towards which AgrifoodTEF customers show most of their interest is weeding (whether fully autonomous or assisted by robot technology). That said, it is interesting to note that in “Robotics” / “Arable farming” value is much more evenly distributed along a range of activity use cases, while in “AI” / “Arable farming” it is almost concentrated on the single activity use case “Observation and Monitoring”.

Figure 2.4: breakdown of service value for the “Robotics” macro use case

“Mainly conformity-related” activities

Let us now go back to the level of activities to consider conformity-related ones.

While their number and weight in AgrifoodTEF’s contract portfolio is significantly lower than the categories considered before, “mainly conformity” activities are relevant in AgrifoodTEF’s portfolio and show signs of numerical growth over time. Indeed, for some partners these activities are becoming a main source of contracts with customers. The reason for this lies probably in the need that many companies developing AI- and robotics-related products have to make sure

that their upcoming products will match the requirement of the evolving normative landscape of the European Union (e.g., the AI Act and the Data Act). Such landscape, in fact, is perceived as sufficiently complex to require support from experts in the field. This is another trend that may provide indications to orient the efforts of the TEF to achieve long-term sustainability.

“Mainly other” activities

To conclude this analysis of activities, it is worth to expend some words on those categorised as “mainly other”.

Our analysis of Service Request Forms showed that these are mainly related to **pre-analysis**. In other terms, most of these activities are related to the request by a customer to AgrifoodTEF to provide an assessment of a customer’s solution, presented either as an actual prototype or simply as a design. The customer asks AgrifoodTEF for expert feedback about the solution’s fitness for purpose and/or its suitability for a given agricultural scenario.

Many of the “mainly other” activities are forms of *desk assessment*, where the customer arrives at AgrifoodTEF with a design for a solution (e.g.: a machine, a system, a piece of software, a service) and asks AgrifoodTEF to evaluate specific elements of it and/or to assess if its features (e.g., the type of sensors to be used in a robotic implement) match the needs—technical or agronomic—of the intended use case. Whenever such an assessment includes significant experimental action (e.g., to prepare a test environment and try different sensors in it) the activity was categorised as “mainly physical”; however, it happened fairly often that the customer asked for a pre-analysis of their technical decisions, without any experimental complement. In these cases, the activity was categorised instead as “mainly other”.

A final note about “mainly other” activities concerns a potentially relevant connection to AgrifoodTEF’s self-sustainability.

Given their nature, many of the activities in the “mainly other” category may easily evolve into contracts for *technical development or co-development*. Being these outside of the scope of the AgrifoodTEF project, any request of this kind by customers gets either turned down or steered outside the project. However, in a post-project scenario where the range of services offered by the TEF is no more subjected to restrictions, *incorporating development and co-development services into the service catalogue may be a relevant factor in ensuring the continued existence and sustainability of the TEF*.

Addressing the differences between today’s market for TEF services and tomorrow’s

The fact that the costs of AgrifoodTEF services are being subsidised by the EU and member states has a profound impact on the long-term sustainability of the TEF. While AgrifoodTEF funding had and is having a key role in allowing the TEF to establish its activities and get the whole “service machine” up to speed, preparing long-term sustainability requires that the TEF plans for the interruption of such subsidy.

A side effect of the fact that companies pay a reduced (or null) fee for AgrifoodTEF services is that their decisions as customers of AgrifoodTEF are only partially indicative of the real market for testing, experimentation and validation services of AI- and robotics-based agrifood solutions in Europe. Nowadays, thanks to the fact that AgrifoodTEF services are heavily subsidised, companies are able to exploit such services without having to divert (significant) funds from

other activities, such as technical development. It remains to be seen how many of our current customers will still make the same decisions when they will be asked to pay for AgrifoodTEF services at full price.

The issue becomes especially critical considering that TEF services are by design focused toward products and services incorporating advanced technology. These are the kind of products that are usually developed by start-ups or otherwise small-and-agile companies. More precisely, these are the kind of companies developing high-technology solutions that do not possess the infrastructure to execute testing and experimental validation internally, and therefore may benefit from AgrifoodTEF services.

After the end of the subsidy of AgrifoodTEF services, in an economic landscape where small companies are usually struggling to get funds to support their activity, such companies may well decide that the very technical—and therefore costly—testing and experimentation services offered by the TEF are out of their possibilities. Large manufacturers of machines and systems for the agrifood sector are, of course, developing their own solutions based on AI and/or robotics. However, such players are likely to prefer executing testing and experimentation internally: both because they already have most of the necessary technical infrastructure (even if not necessarily also the expertise needed to meaningfully evaluate such systems) and because they are by nature more wary of sharing their intellectual property with others.

For these reasons, after the end of the AgrifoodTEF project the TEF may face a lack of customers for testing and experimentation services. In this scenario, a possible way to find customers would be to expand the TEF's service portfolio to incorporate services providing technical development and co-development. As explained at the end of the previous subsection, while these services are currently not within the TEF's scope, there appears to exist a significant demand for them. Most importantly, the type of small companies and start-ups that may decide not to invest in services focused purely on testing and experimentation may decide to invest instead in development services, since they are perceived as more crucial to the company's success than the former.

3. Preparing sustainability: the role of digital services

A crucial difference between digital services and the other types of service in the AgrifoodTEF catalogue is that the operating cost of providing a digital service can be much lower. As highlighted by the definition provided in Section 2, digital services *“do not require physical interaction with the customer's solution for the service to take place, and can be accessed remotely”*. This has significant consequences. Among them:

- For most digital services, most or all of the execution can be done by computers. The intervention of human operators (if any) is usually required only to set up the operations.
- Digital services do not require to physically move people nor equipment: a costly and time-consuming activity.
- Data are *“inherently non-rivalrous, non-exclusive and inexhaustible”* (see Annex 1 for an analysis of the consequences of this for AgrifoodTEF). The same datasets can be re-used to provide multiple services without degradation and without need (nor costs) to collect and prepare it. This requires that the IPR management of datasets allows them to be (re)used in this way: a topic tackled in Section 4.

For all these reasons, most digital services have a key property: **once they have been developed, the operational cost to execute them is low.**

For instance, let us consider a digital service providing a customer with access to high-fidelity simulations of a sunflower field. Access is done via a remote interface that allows the user to upload their own robot's model and its behaviours, and to collect the output of the simulator. The simulation covers a range of different climate conditions and caters for all stages in the development of the sunflower crop; additionally, it can simulate the effect of the most common diseases and pests. Finally, position and distribution of the plants are fully adjustable to represent different cultivation styles. The simulation also comprises the effect of environmental features such as season, time of day and possibly even atmospheric phenomena like rain or fog. Developing such a simulation system is a very costly process, as it requires to:

- set up and configure a suitable simulation engine;
- configure or develop any specialised module that needs to interact with the engine (e.g., fog simulator);
- assemble and set up the hardware needed to execute it;
- develop the interfaces allowing users to access the system;
- use physical equipment and suitable cultivations to collect source data to use in the development of the simulated environment, repeating this operation for each environmental condition (e.g., different EU countries, different periods of the year);
- test, debug, validate the whole system and each of its components.

However, once the service has been set up, the only cost items associated to the *execution* of the service are those concerning the operation and maintenance of the hardware. This is typical of digital services, and marks a major difference from every other type of AgrifoodTEF service: except for digital ones, in fact, services have an operational cost that does not decrease drastically as they are provided repeatedly. There are, of course, savings due to streamlining of the services and gains in personnel experience: but the main sources of costs, i.e. those related to the time expended by people and to the need to employ specialised equipment, cannot be reduced by much.

For these reasons we expect digital services to play a key role in the self-sustainability of the TEF after the end of the AgrifoodTEF project: they can, in fact, provide a significant source of revenue while accounting for a minor quota of the operational costs of the organisation. It is conceivable that, in a hypothetical post-project scenario, the cost of physical TEF services may get partly subsidised by the revenue generated by digital services, thus allowing the TEF to keep the cost of physical services acceptable to their intended customers while maintaining their availability in the catalogue.

4. Building sustainability tools

So far we have analysed the information that Service Request Forms provide about the activities that customers ask AgrifoodTEF to perform (Section 2), and we have outlined the reasons why digital services are expected to play an

important role in ensuring the self-sustainability of the TEF after the end of the AgrifoodTEF project (Section 3). Section 4 examines some key elements needed to ensure the continued existence and operation of the TEF, i.e.:

- a policy to manage the Intellectual Property Rights associated to the data generated by services;
- the AgrifoodTEF Dataspace;
- the AgrifoodTEF's digital infrastructure.

Since both the Dataspace and the digital infrastructure are the object of their own dedicated M36 Deliverable, the bulk of Section 4 is dedicated to the first item. For what concern the other two, we will limit our discussion to explaining their relation with AgrifoodTEF's self-sustainability.

IPR management for data generated by AgrifoodTEF services

Work Package 2 of AgrifoodTEF identifies the management of Intellectual Property Rights concerning datasets as a key item to ensure the long-term success and sustainability of the TEF's actions. As explained in Section 3, the higher potential margin of revenues associated to digital services with respect to other types of service may be crucial to ensure the financial sustainability of the whole TEF. In order to let digital services fulfil this role, two conditions must be met:

- digital services must be able to leverage a sufficiently large and diverse *corpus* of data;
- control of such *corpus* of data must remain inside the TEF.

The first condition can be satisfied if AgrifoodTEF partners add to the *corpus* the datasets that they create as output or byproduct of AgrifoodTEF services. The second condition implies that the data generated by services are not "given away", but instead their control is maintained by the TEF. This ensures that when external parties (e.g., companies) are interested in benefiting from such data, they will have to purchase suitable services from AgrifoodTEF. This in turn requires that AgrifoodTEF maintains (sufficient) control of the data generated by services: i.e., that a suitable Intellectual Property Rights policy for data is in place.

IPR policy for data

Work on IPR regulations within AgrifoodTEF is managed by WP4 (specifically, Task T4.2). However, given the importance that IPR for data has for AgrifoodTEF, WP2 has offered to WP4 to contribute on this specific aspect. As part of this contribution, WP2 has studied the issue and prepared a proposal for an **IPR policy for data**.

AgrifoodTEF's IPR policy for data is a legal document developed by Politecnico di Milano's legal staff under the guidance of POLIMI's WP2 team. Its origin lies in the discussions about IPR policy which took place in the face-to-face project meeting of June 2024 in Poznan. Those discussions, in fact, defined the project's orientation towards IPR for data. For reasons similar to those outlined by Section 3, the main decision taken in Poznan was to "*define an IPR policy on data that maintains control of data generated by the project inside AgrifoodTEF, both during and beyond the life of the project*".

POLIMI asked its legal team to prepare a draft of the IPR policy for data according to the criteria defined in Poznan. The policy was based upon the idea of building a *Joint Dataset*: a collection of datasets generated by AgrifoodTEF services which was jointly owned by all partners. The Joint Dataset would be available to AgrifoodTEF partners for exploitation according to the provisions of the IPR policy for data. The guiding principles behind the proposed IPR policy are listed hereafter.

- Define a framework to protect and enhance over time the value of the data assets generated by AgrifoodTEF, collectively addressed with the term Joint Dataset.
- Ensure smooth integration of this policy with the Consortium Agreement.
- Allow customers to benefit from AgrifoodTEF's datasets while ensuring:
- That interaction of customers with AgrifoodTEF's data happens without AgrifoodTEF losing control of the data (i.e., without allowing the customers to get copies of the data).
- That companies can share their own IP with AgrifoodTEF (if required for the execution of services) without having to relinquish control of it.
- That services provided by AgrifoodTEF to companies generate value both for the company and for the Joint Dataset.
- That incorporation of data generated during the execution of AgrifoodTEF services into the company's own IP is possible.
- Allow individual partners of AgrifoodTEF to execute their own activities (internal and external to AgrifoodTEF, non-profit and for-profit, during and after the project) without disturbance.
- Define exploitation mechanisms for the Joint Dataset that allow individual partners to leverage it for their activities, while ensuring that activities benefiting from the Joint Dataset also contribute to the Joint Dataset.
- Set up governance mechanisms for the Joint Dataset, considering both the phase when the AgrifoodTEF project is ongoing and the subsequent phase when the project is completed.

The first draft also defined the governance of the Joint Dataset, with the aim of ensuring protection of Joint Dataset, both during and after AgrifoodTEF's lifespan. The overarching goal of the IPR policy for data was, in fact, to set up mechanisms able to support the TEF's self-sustainability after 2027. Without going into the details of the proposed IPR policy for data, the following two figures illustrate how it manages the two main use cases considered by the policy, i.e.:

- **services to externals**, i.e. provision of AgrifoodTEF to customers;
- **internal commercial use**, where the Joint Dataset is used by a partner to perform internal activities that benefit the partner (such as building tools or developing products and services).

The most important element of Figures 4.1 and 4.2 are the arrows showing how some of the datasets produced by AgrifoodTEF services are *inbound* while others are *outbound*, depending on the fact that they become part of the Joint Dataset or not.

Figure 4.1: proposed management of IPR (AgrifoodTEF services to externals)

Internal Commercial Use for the benefit of Partner A

Figure 4.2: proposed management of IPR (internal commercial use)

The first draft of the proposal for an IPR policy for data was presented by WP2 and WP4 to the project partners on October 18th, 2024. At that time, discussions were started with all project partners to gauge their reactions and orientations, and to gather feedback for the further development of the IPR policy. A more formal request for feedback was done during a specific session on the IPR policy for data organised at the face-to-face project meeting held in Brussels in November 2024. Further discussion and a new request for feedback took place during the project meetings which accompanied the project review of March 2025 in Cordoba.

Over time, it became apparent that few partners were willing to provide feedback about the proposed IPR policy. Part of the reason was, probably, that it was a legal document requiring effort to be fully understood, and possibly the help of legal professionals. However, that was probably not the whole reason. Several partners, while never openly criticising the proposed IPR policy, nonetheless seemed worried that it may interfere with their existing activities and business model, or otherwise constrain their activities during and beyond the duration of the project. Some partners appeared to be worried, in particular, at the difficulties that signing a legally binding document about data control may introduce in their execution of projects involving companies requiring strict non-disclosure regimes.

The final outcome of the lack of reaction by most partners to the proposed IPR policy for data was that it proved difficult to finalise it, and that the actual agreement of all (or most) of AgrifoodTEF partners towards signing such a document was not to be taken for granted.

For the reasons listed above POLIMI decided to explore an alternative approach towards IPR for data based on the concept of license. This new approach was presented at the face-to-face project meeting held in Uppsala in September 2025. A series of use cases concerning AgrifoodTEF services involving the generation and/or exploitation of datasets were presented, and licensing mechanisms to govern access to the data and the revenues associated to services were outlined and discussed. This new, license-based, approach appeared indeed to be closer to what many partners desired from AgrifoodTEF, so a decision was taken between WP4 and WP2 to try and pursue it.

The task of rewriting the proposed IPR policy for data in terms of a licensing scheme is not a trivial one. First of all, because it needs a redesign of the entire mechanism; secondly, because it necessarily requires, again, the involvement of legal professionals. The preparation of the first proposal for an IPR policy for data already showed how both these aspects are very complex to manage, and require long times to arrive at satisfactory results, even before partner feedback is involved. Also, it is difficult to predict how partners (and their legal offices) would react when presented with the new IPR policy in the form of a legal document needing their signatures. For these reasons, work towards a new proposal was temporarily stalled while WP2 looked for an alternative approach.

Fortunately, a (likely) more effective alternative was identified, as explained below.

The AgrifoodTEF Dataspace as IPR management tool

In the second half of 2025, the activity on the AgrifoodTEF Dataspace reached the stage where partners were able to publish datasets onto the Dataspace, and to have a first-person experience with the tools that the Dataspace provides to data owners to flexibly manage access to such data. By combining this experience with the already acquired knowledge about the needs of AgrifoodTEF in terms of IPR management for data, it emerged that the AgrifoodTEF Dataspace, in its being a tool to flexibly manage access to data, can also be used to *implicitly define and enforce an IPR policy*, without requiring data owners to sign legal documents.

The AgrifoodTEF Dataspace offers this possibility as a side effect of its main use as an instrument to manage interactions between the providers of digital resources and the consumers of such resources. The Dataspace allows AgrifoodTEF to pursue an alternative approach to setting up and enforcing an IPR policy for data: i.e., by *embedding it in the Dataspace's very structure and operation*. One of the key points of the Dataspace is that data owners (and particularly AgrifoodTEF partners publishing resources on the Dataspace) can finely manage access levels to the data, differentiating between different categories of users such as Consortium members or AgrifoodTEF customers, or even on a user-by-user basis. This flexibility is expected to let AgrifoodTEF partners define customised ways to manage access to their datasets, thus matching the (possibly heterogeneous) requirements of their services and projects, both within and outside AgrifoodTEF.

Most importantly, the Dataspace's allows a data owner to allow another party's software to interact with the owner's data *without providing them with access to the data* (and thus removing the possibility for the other party to duplicate the data). In this scenario, interaction with the data takes the form of the software running, with the restricted data as its input, in a "data room": i.e., an isolated processing environment controlled by the data owner. The only thing that leaves the data room at the end of the processing is the output of the other party's software, which the data owner can inspect before delivery to prevent data exfiltration. Particularly interesting for AgrifoodTEF is the fact that the data rooms provided by the Dataspace also allow AgrifoodTEF partner B to run software (e.g., train an AI model)

on the data owned by AgrifoodTEF Partner A without A disclosing the data to B: this is relevant, for instance, when A's data is subject to an NDA between Partner A and a company.

All in all, the tools for data access provided by the Dataspace are expected to allow AgrifoodTEF to define more granular ways to access data with respect to the black-and-white world of "full access" versus "no access", and to tailor access provisions, where needed, on a dataset-by-dataset basis. Those ways appear to be sufficiently flexible to allow every partner to configure access to each piece of their own data in a way that is both satisfactory to the data owner and suitable for supporting AgrifoodTEF's work, including allowing other partners (limited) permission to use the data. This approach is probably better suited to the needs of AgrifoodTEF partners with respect to a single overarching IPR policy, and does not require partners to take commitments as legal entities.

The Dataspace-based approach to the management of IPR for data was presented by POLIMI to Work Package 2 partners in December 2025 during one of WP2's periodic meeting, where it appears to have encountered a favourable reaction. Importantly, in that occasion the members of WP2 who are most involved in the design and setup of the AgrifoodTEF Dataspace confirmed that the Dataspace possesses all the tools necessary for the feasibility of the proposed approach. Shortly afterwards, POLIMI discussed the Dataspace-based approach with Work Package 4 leader Josephinum Research. JR approved the idea and accepted POLIMI's offer to continue its collaboration with WP4 about IPR for data pursuing this new approach.

For the time being it is still too early to declare with certainty if the Dataspace-mediated approach to IPR management for data is viable and –more critically– if it suits the needs of all AgrifoodTEF partners. We plan to start project-wide discussions about these topics at the face-to-face project meeting that will take place in February 2026 in Paris.

AgrifoodTEF's IPR policy for data and the EUCC

At the face-to-face project meeting in Cordoba emerged one additional issue concerning the IPR policy for data. Some partners expressed concern that the way AgrifoodTEF is planning to manage the IPR for data generated by AgrifoodTEF services may conflict with the *EU Code of conduct on agricultural data sharing by contractual agreement*. The EUCC is a voluntary code proposed to operators of the agri-food domain by a collection of stakeholders in 2018, and includes provisions to manage the IPR of data collected during agricultural operations.

As a further contribution to the work of WP4 on IPR-connected issues, WP2 executed an analysis of the points of contact (and of possible conflict) between the proposed IPR policy of AgrifoodTEF and the EUCC. The same analysis tackled also the interactions (and possible conflicts) between the EU Data Act and the proposed IPR policy.

The outcome of such analysis is a document which has been incorporated into this Deliverable as Annex 1. The reader is pointed to it for the full picture; here we simply provide its conclusions, which are the following.

- There is no conflict between AgrifoodTEF's approach to IPR for data and the EU Data Act.
- There is no conflict between AgrifoodTEF's approach to IPR for data and the EUCC.

The AgrifoodTEF Dataspace

The AgrifoodTEF Dataspace plays an important part in the long-term sustainability of the TEF. Its task is to manage interactions between the providers and consumers of digital resources, as well as to act as a marketplace for them. Among the digital resources that the AgrifoodTEF Dataspace allows its users to publish and use are:

- datasets;
- computing resources (e.g., the HPC servers needed to train large AI models);
- access to remote systems (e.g., simulators);
- algorithms (i.e., software);
- complete digital services leveraging one or more of the above.

One of the reasons why the Dataspace is important to the sustainability of AgrifoodTEF is that (as explained in Section 3) digital services have a crucial role to play for the TEF's continued existence; therefore the Dataspace must be able to support them in an effective way. A second reason for the importance of the Dataspace comes from the discussion on IPR: the Dataspace, in fact, is expected to play a key role in enabling the management of Intellectual Property Rights associated to data.

We will not go into more detail about AgrifoodTEF Dataspace development and features, pointing the reader towards the specific Deliverable dedicated to these topics (D2.8 - AgrifoodTEF data space Y3).

AgrifoodTEF's digital infrastructure

The operation of AgrifoodTEF, and particularly of its digital services, requires a complex technical machinery comprising digital assets (e.g., data and associated metadata) and resources (e.g., servers and associated network infrastructure). This machinery is also needed to set up, operate and make available to its users the AgrifoodTEF Dataspace.

So far, AgrifoodTEF's digital infrastructure has been built out of resources provided by the project partners, and the requirements on it have been (especially because the Dataspace is still in development) modest. However, digital infrastructure will gain more and more importance as the AgrifoodTEF project approaches its conclusion, since it must be ready to support the continued operation of the TEF without disruptions and with a clear attribution of its operational costs.

For all these reasons we are listing AgrifoodTEF's digital infrastructure here as one of the key tools for the long-term sustainability of the TEF. For an in-depth analysis and a snapshot of the current state of AgrifoodTEF's digital infrastructure we point the reader towards the specific Deliverable dedicated to these topics (D2.4 - AgrifoodTEF digital infrastructure documentation Y3).

5. Conclusions

For AgrifoodTEF, Y3 (2025) has marked a step change in service provision to customers. Before Y3, much of the partner's effort has been devoted to the design and setup of services; with Y3, effort has moved to the execution, streamlining and optimisation of services. At the beginning of December 2025 the number of services negotiated with customers was over 450, of which a significant fraction are digital services: i.e., the focus of this Deliverable.

For what concerns this document, the reached maturity in service provision enables a switch of viewpoint. For the first time, we have been able to move the approach of this yearly overview of services from *open-loop* (i.e., driven by partners' previsions and previous experience) to *closed-loop*, i.e. driven by the actual demands and expectations of our customers. To this change approach corresponds a greater importance given, in D2.16, to outlining possible mechanisms for the self-sustainability of the TEF after the five years of AgrifoodTEF. Indeed, as stated in Section 1, the goals of this document are (i) to understand the market for AgrifoodTEF services and (ii) to provide indications to set up sustainability mechanisms.

Section 2 and Section 3 pursue the document's goals through an analysis of the *activities* contracted between AgrifoodTEF and its customers. Service Request Forms describe the features of each one of the 241 activities –each usually composed of multiple services– contracted so far. The analysis of SRFs provided by Sections 2 and 3 is therefore relevant to understand both our current market and how we can expect it to evolve after the end of the project (when the cost of services will not be subsidised anymore by EU and national funding agencies). Additionally, such analysis provides guidelines about possible strategies for long-term sustainability.

The most relevant outcomes of Section 2 and Section 3, in view of this document's goals, are summarised below. Elements **in bold** correspond to actionable guidelines about **actions to promote the sustainability of the TEF** after the end of the AgrifoodTEF project.

- The current market for AgrifoodTEF activities can be subdivided into “mainly physical” (48%), “mainly digital” (32%) and “mainly conformity-related” (12%) activities. A small but non-trivial percentage (7%) concerns “mainly other” activities (more about these below).
- Among “mainly physical” activities, a very significant fraction (45%) is focused on *creating and providing datasets*: for this reason, such “mainly physical” activities can be seen as preliminary to future digital activities, i.e. providing again the same datasets (now readily available) to different customers. According to this view, digital activities are expected to increase their importance for AgrifoodTEF as a more and more comprehensive *corpus* of data becomes available. Additionally, it emerges as an important point that AgrifoodTEF sets up an Intellectual Property Rights policy to support the **use of the same datasets to provide services to multiple customers** (more about this below).
- Digital services are the only category where the cost to operate the service is usually much lower than the cost to set it up. For this reason, one key element to the self-sustainability of the TEF is expected to be the reliance on the revenue from such services. The possibility of **using the revenue from digital services to subsidise physical services** (which have a much higher operational cost) should be considered.

- Among “mainly digital” activities, most of the customer’s demand is oriented towards those concerning AI models. For sustainability, AgrifoodTEF should therefore make sure to be able to **optimally meet such demand**.
- “Mainly conformity-related” activities, while accounting for a minor part of the total, intercept a key need of our customer base: i.e., to be supported in ensuring the compliance of their solutions with EU’s regulations concerning products which incorporate AI and/or robotics. It is important for AgrifoodTEF to **provide services able to satisfy this demand**.
- “Mainly other” activities appear to be mostly about *pre-analysis*. While this type of activity will probably remain interesting to our market, our analysis shows that many pre-analysis activities have the potential to evolve into, or give rise to, further services centered on *development* or *co-development*. Such services, while out of scope for AgrifoodTEF, may come to be a major source of revenue for the TEF, and fit very well with the research background of most AgrifoodTEF partners. Therefore, **introducing technology development services** in the catalogue of the TEF may have a significant impact in increasing its capability to self-sustain. An additional bonus of this approach is that it could help the TEF continue to sell services to start-ups and other small companies; these, in fact, may not consider “testing and experimentation” services valuable enough to spend their limited resources on them, but are usually very interested in receiving technological support.

Section 4 tackles three specific elements that have particular and direct relevance to the self-sustainability of AgrifoodTEF, i.e: the IPR policy for data (already mentioned before); the AgrifoodTEF Dataspace; AgrifoodTEF’s digital infrastructure. Considering that the last two elements are the object of specific M36 Deliverables, the main focus of Section 4 is on IPR. Its main outcomes are summarised below.

- Defining and implementing a suitable IPR policy for data is important to AgrifoodTEF’s long-term sustainability.
- An IPR policy for data supporting the self-sustainability of the TEF should support the generation of a *corpus* of high-quality datasets upon which to build high-value digital services. Crucially, the policy should ensure that the TEF maintains the control of the datasets, so that they can be exploited to provide services to multiple customers.
- Approaching the definition of an IPR policy for data by crafting a legal document to complement the Consortium Agreement proved very difficult. An alternative and more promising approach appears to be the *use of the AgrifoodTEF Dataspace to embed the IPR policy*. Such approach has multiple advantages, including the possibility for data owners to manage access rights flexibly, on a dataset-by-dataset and/or user-by-user basis.
- In view of the features that the IPR policy for data should possess to promote sustainability, the AgrifoodTEF Dataspace provides a key tool, i.e. *data rooms*. Data rooms allow customers (more precisely: their software) to interact with TEF datasets without providing the customer with access to the data. Data rooms can also be used to manage interactions between the data published on the AgrifoodTEF Dataspace by TEF partners and other partners of the TEF: in particular, it could be used by data owners to enable other partners to use their data without compromising any non-disclosure agreements protecting the data.

The remaining two sections of this document are these Conclusions and Annex 1. Annex 1 is a focused analysis of the possible conflicts between the way AgrifoodTEF intends to tackle IPR for data and two external IPR-related regulations. The first is the EU Data Act; the second a pre-existing voluntary code of conduct defined by stakeholders in the agricultural machinery field. The analysis of Annex 1 confirms that no conflict exists and provides some guidelines on how IPR can be managed in the contracts signed between AgrifoodTEF service providers and their customers.

Annex 1 – Analysis of the impact on AgrifoodTEF’s IPR policy for data of the EU Data Act and the EUCC

Control of data generated by AgrifoodTEF services: brief analysis and proposed approach

Context

We will limit the scope of this analysis to AgrifoodTEF services that have the potential to generate new data. The workflow of an AgrifoodTEF service of this type is the following (keywords are highlighted):

- A **customer** brings to a **partner** of AgrifoodTEF a **system** to be tested and/or validated and/or certified. The system can be, for instance: a device, a component of a device, a piece of software, an algorithm, a service. The customer is a company.
- The AgrifoodTEF partner provides to the customer a service which includes an experimental activity involving the customer’s system.
- The experimental activity performed by AgrifoodTEF may require that the system is operated in environments that are under control of a third party: for the sake of this analysis, we will focus on the case where (part of) the experimental activity environment occurs in a cultivation owned by a **farmer**.
- Due to the experimental activity associated to the service, the system under test and/or AgrifoodTEF’s own systems produce **data**, some of which captures aspects (e.g., images) of the farmer’s cultivation.

The problems tackled by this document are:

- Who is the owner of the data produced during experimental activity?
- What is the nature of the data produced during experimental activity?
- How should AgrifoodTEF regulate the use of data produced during experimental activity? Who should be involved in such regulation?

The following sections answer, in turn, each of these questions. The document then concludes with a proposal for a general approach to managing control of data generated in the context of AgrifoodTEF services.

Who is the owner of the data produced during experimental activity?

The key point here is that the concept of “data ownership” is not the correct one to be considered. Data ownership, in fact, is not easily defined, and indeed it is not defined at all by EU law, including the [Data Act](#). The Data Act, which entered into force on 11 January 2024 and will become applicable in September 2025, is the most important EU regulation concerning data generated by AgrifoodTEF services. The [General Data Protection Regulation](#) (GDPR) is generally not relevant in this context, as it focuses on personal data.

The reason why the concept of “ownership” is not necessarily applicable is that data are inherently non-rivalrous, non-exclusive and inexhaustible, and therefore different from physical goods, for which the concept

has been developed [1]. For data, the correct concepts to be considered in alternative to “ownership” are those of *data access* and *usage rights*. Any activity generating data should therefore regulate (e.g., via contracts) their access and usage rights.

The issue concerning “ownership” is also recognised by the *EU Code of conduct on agricultural data sharing by contractual agreement* (EUCC) [2]. The EUCC is a voluntary code proposed to operators of the agri-food domain by a collection of stakeholders in 2018 (thus predating the Data Act). The main goal of the EUCC is to push operators in the agri-food domain to adopt as a standard practice the contractual regulation of data management. The actual adoption of the EUCC by stakeholders is not easily gauged [3], but arguably the approach of AgrifoodTEF towards data should aim, if possible, at being compatible with the EUCC.

The EUCC identifies the “Data originator” as the key figure in data control:

[the] Data originator (sometimes referred as “owner”) is generally defined as “the person or entity that can claim the exclusive right to license access to the data and control its downstream use or re-use”, i.e. the party that the data is attributed to. The data originator of all the data generated during the operation is the one who has created/collected this data either by technical means (e.g., agricultural machinery, electronic data processing programs), by themselves or who has commissioned data providers for this purpose.

According to this definition, in the context of AgrifoodTEF services the only data originators are the customer and/or the AgrifoodTEF partner executing the service.

What is the nature of the data produced during experimental activity?

Copyrights and database rights are the main relevant intellectual property rights concerning data [1]. Copyrights mainly apply to works that can be considered an individual expression of their author(s), and as such are not suitable for AgrifoodTEF-generated data. Database protection, on the other hand, is more suitable.

Database protection is based on EU’s [Database Directive](#). Databases qualify for copyright protection if they constitute the author's own intellectual creation by reason of the selection or arrangement of their contents, which matches poorly with AgrifoodTEF’s data.

However, there is a second mechanism that allows databases to qualify for copyright protection. The Database Directive established a so-called *sui generis* right (“database right”) for the makers of databases, irrespective of whether they qualify for copyright. The database right is granted *whenever the maker had to undertake a qualitatively and/or quantitatively substantial investment in either the obtaining, verification or presentation of the contents of the database*. Through the database right, makers of databases can benefit from legal protections even when there is no particular originality to their work, but there was nonetheless a substantial investment involved in bringing it about [1]. This type of protection appears to match very well the features of the data generated as a consequence of AgrifoodTEF services.

How should AgrifoodTEF regulate the use of data produced during experimental activity? Who should be involved in such regulation?

The EU Data Act requires that usage rights associated to the data produced by the experimental activity of an AgrifoodTEF service are stated in the agreements (e.g., contract) preceding the execution of the activity. However, for what concerns the provision of AgrifoodTEF services to customers the Data Act does not seem to pose significant limitations on the content of such agreements [4]. AgrifoodTEF should be able, then, to choose the most suitable approach to data control.

According to the Data Act, beside the AgrifoodTEF partner providing the service and the customer, it does not seem to be necessary to include other parties in the contractual control of data produced during the service [4]. In particular, it does not appear to be required an involvement of the farmer, thus simplifying the contractual aspect of service negotiation. The key point is that in the execution of an AgrifoodTEF service the farmer is never the “user”, but simply a provider of (part of) the means to execute the service. If a “user” (i.e., the party that the Data Act most protects) can be identified in AgrifoodTEF service provision, it is the customer.

The only case where contractual involvement of the farmer is needed occurs if data resulting from the service include *personal data* concerning the farmer. This case, however, is not expected to occur. Additionally, management of personal data would introduce significant additional obligations for AgrifoodTEF according to the EU General Data Protection Regulation. It is therefore highly advisable to avoid any collection of personal data during the execution of AgrifoodTEF services.

For what concerns the EUCC, it instructs the parties involved in data generation to “establish a contract clearly setting the data collection and data sharing conditions”: establishing awareness about the opportunity of regulating data by contract is indeed the focus of the EUCC. In order to be compatible with the EUCC, AgrifoodTEF should therefore ensure that the contracts defining the features of services to customers always contain a section concerning data, which is the same indication coming from the Data Act.

According to the EUCC, the parties involved in the contractual agreement about data generated by an AgrifoodTEF service should be limited to the “Data originators”, i.e. the AgrifoodTEF partner(s) providing the service and the customer. The farmer is not considered as a necessary party in the contract.

Conclusions and proposed approach

The constraints that the EU Data Act impose to the management of data collected or generated in the execution of AgrifoodTEF services essentially reduce to the fact that it is necessary to regulate access and usage rights concerning the data.

The proposed approach is therefore to **always incorporate in the contract defining an AgrifoodTEF service a section concerning data access and usage rights**. Such section can be either written specifically for the individual contract, or it can reference a general AgrifoodTEF IPR policy for data.

The parties to the contract (and particularly to its section concerning data) **should be the AgrifoodTEF partner** providing the service **and the customer** benefiting from the service. No requirement exists to involve other parties into the agreements, such as the farmer providing the cultivation where experimental activity takes place. This holds true even if data about the farmer's cultivation are captured and stored during the execution of the service.

The proposed approach is fully compatible with the EU Code of conduct on agricultural data sharing by contractual agreement (EUCC).

Bibliography for Annex 1

[1] [What is data ownership, and does it still matter under EU data law? An exploration of traditional concepts of data ownership, and of the expected impact of the Data Act](#) by the European Commission, Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology, Unit G.1 Data Policy and Innovation

[2] [EU Code of conduct on agricultural data sharing by contractual agreement \(EUCC\)](#)

[3] [The future of agricultural data-sharing policy in Europe: stakeholder insights on the EU Code of Conduct](#) by Mark Ryan, Can Atik, Kelly Rijswijk, Marc-Jeroen Bogaardt, Eva Maes & Ella Deroo - *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, volume 11, 1197 (2024)

[4] [Data Act explained](#) by the European Commission

[5] [What is the impact of the EU Data Act on Agritech? How to extract new value from the use of machinery and applications in agriculture - a look at the Data Act](#) by Osborne-Clark Consulting

